

A New Origin of the Loop Coefficients of the Electron Anomalous Magnetic Moment

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Abstract

The loop coefficients of the electron anomalous magnetic moment arise from Feynman diagram contributions to the correction to the electron magnetic moment in the perturbative expansion of QED. We find a close relationship between these loop coefficients and some basic physical constants. This suggests that there may be a new origin of loop coefficients.

Introduction

The correction formula of electron anomalous magnetic moment [1] is as follows:

$$a_e^{theor.} = a_e^{QED} + a_e^{had} + a_e^{weak} + a_e^{grav} \quad (1)$$

In the pure QED correction [2], the electron's anomalous magnetic moment is expanded as a power of the coupling constant α (the fine-structure constant):

$$A_1 = A_1^{(2)} \left(\frac{\alpha}{\pi}\right) + A_1^{(4)} \left(\frac{\alpha}{\pi}\right)^2 + A_1^{(6)} \left(\frac{\alpha}{\pi}\right)^3 + A_1^{(8)} \left(\frac{\alpha}{\pi}\right)^4 + A_1^{(10)} \left(\frac{\alpha}{\pi}\right)^5 + \dots \quad (2)$$

The coefficients of each order of the electron anomalous magnetic moment are as follows:

Table 1: loop coefficients [3]

n	$A_1^{(2n)}$	$C_e^{(2n)}$
1	1/2	0.5
2	-0.328478965579193...	-0.32847844400
3	1.181241456587...	1.181234017
4	-1.912245764...	-1.91132213891(88)
5	6.080(160)	6.08(16)

In Table 1, $A_1^{(2n)}$ is the loop coefficient in pure electron QED. $C_e^{(2n)}$ is the total coefficient for loops of all orders.

We have found the following relationships: (In this paper, g_e , g_μ , and g_n are negative)

The relationship between $C_e^{(2n)}$ and g_p :

$$C_e^2 + C_e^4 + C_e^6 + C_e^8 = C_e^{T4} \approx -\frac{g_p}{10} \quad (3)$$

That is:

$$0.5 + (-0.328478444) + 1.181234017 + (-1.91132213891) = -0.55856656591 \quad (4)$$

Here, g_p is the spin g-factor of the proton, and its value is 5.5856946893. The value of $-g_p/10$ is -0.55856946893 . This is very close to the result obtained from equation (3).

$-g_p/10$ and C_e^{T4} are also related as follows:

$$\frac{-g_p/10}{C_e^{T4}} = \left[\frac{(g_e/2)^4}{1 + 2\alpha/\pi} \right]^5 \quad (5)$$

Here, g_e is the g-factor of the electron spin.

The value on the left-hand side of equation (5) is 1.0000051973; the value on the right-hand side is 1.0000051998.

$A_1^{(8)}$ is similar to $g_n/2$, and their relationship is as follows:

$$\frac{g_n}{2} \cdot \left[\frac{g_e}{2} \cdot \frac{g_p - g_n(g_\mu/g_e)^5}{3\pi} \right]^2 = A_1^{(8)} \quad (6)$$

Here, g_n and g_μ are the spin g-factors of neutrons and muons.

The value on the left side of Equation (6) is -1.912245764849 ; the value of $A_1^{(8)}$ is $-1.912245764 \dots$

C_e^6 is very close to $\sqrt{g_p}/2$, and their relationship is as follows:

$$\left(\frac{\sqrt{g_p}/2}{C_e^6} \right)^2 \approx \frac{m_n/m_p}{\sqrt{g_\mu}/2} \quad (7)$$

The value on the left-hand side of equation (7) is 1.00079543, and the value on the right-hand side is 1.0079517. In this case, $C_e^6 = 1.181234017$.

The relationship between $A_1^{(4)}$ and $287/225$:

$$\frac{2\pi}{5000} \frac{m_n}{m_p} \left[\frac{7^2 \alpha}{\left(\frac{287}{225} + \frac{g_n}{3}\right)} \frac{m_e}{m_p} \right]^{-1/3} = \left(A_1^{(4)}\right)^6 \quad (8)$$

From Equation (8), we obtain: $|A_1^{(4)}| = 0.32847896532$. $287/225$ is derived from here [5].

$$A_1^{(4)} = -0.32847896557 \dots$$

The relationship between $C_e^{(2n)}$, $A_1^{(2n)}$, and g_τ :

$$\frac{\alpha^{-1}}{(C_e^6 - C_e^8 - C_e^4)^4} \approx \frac{g_\tau}{2} \quad (9)$$

Here, g_τ is the theoretical value of the spin g-factor for the tau lepton, which is $2 \times 1.001177171(39)$ [4].

The value on the left-hand side of equation (9) is 1.000461691 , and the value on the right-hand side is 1.000471700 .

The relationship between $C_e^{(2n)}$, $A_1^{(2n)}$, and the mass ratio:

$$\frac{\alpha^2}{(C_e^6 - A_1^{(8)} - C_e^4)^8} = \left[\frac{m_n - m_p}{m_p} - g_e \cdot \frac{m_e}{m_p} \right] \cdot \frac{m_\tau}{m_e} \cdot \frac{g_\mu}{g_e} \quad (10)$$

Here, m_n , m_p , m_e , and m_τ represent the masses of the neutron, proton, electron, and tau lepton, respectively.

The value on the left-hand side of equation (10) is 1.001217165 , and the value on the right-hand side is 1.001217218 .

Conclusion

We find some relationships between the loop coefficients of the electron anomalous moment and certain fundamental physical constants, which may indicate that the loop coefficients have other sources.

References

- [1] T. Aoyama, T. Kinoshita, and M. Nio, Theory of the Anomalous Magnetic Moment of the Electron, *Atoms* **7**, 28 (2019).
- [2] S. Laporta, High-precision calculation of the 4-loop contribution to the electron $g-2$ in QED, *Phys. Lett. B* **772**, 232-238 (2017).
- [3] P. J. Mohr, D. B. Newell, B. N. Taylor, and E. Tiesinga, CODATA Recommended Values of the Fundamental Physical Constants: 2022, *J. Phys. Chem. Ref. Data* **54**, 033105 (2025).
- [4] A. Keshavarzi, D. Nomura, and T. Teubner, The $g - 2$ of charged leptons, $\alpha(M_Z^2)$ and the hyperfine splitting of muonium, *Phys. Rev. D* **101**, 014029 (2020). [arXiv:1911.00367v2 [hep-ph]]
- [5] Li Shanhong, Strange Phenomenon of Proton Magnetic Moment, *Zenodo* (2026). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19859137>.